

Study of Neutrosophic b -continuous maps in Neutrosophic Topological Spaces

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Abstract. Neutrosophic sets were introduced to deal with indeterminacy and persistent issues and they were used to develop the neutrosophic topological spaces. In this paper, the concept of neutrosophic b -continuous maps and strongly neutrosophic b -continuous maps are defined and some important properties are developed. We prove that every neutrosophic strongly b -continuous map is a neutrosophic b -continuous map. We examine the relationship of neutrosophic b -continuous maps with the already defined continuous maps such as neutrosophic semi-continuous maps, neutrosophic pre-continuous maps, neutrosophic α -continuous maps. We prove that if a map is any of these neutrosophic continuous map, then that is a neutrosophic b -continuous map. Further, we prove that the surjective neutrosophic b -continuous image of a neutrosophic b -connected space, and a neutrosophic b -compact space is a neutrosophic b -connected space, and neutrosophic b -compact space respectively.

Keywords: Neutrosophic topological spaces; Neutrosophic b -open sets; Neutrosophic b -Continuous map.

1. Introduction

To avert obstacles dealing with ambiguous data, fuzzy sets [25], intuitionistic fuzzy sets [2], vague sets [6], rough sets [11], and soft sets [10] were introduced as mathematical tools. All these approaches have their implicit crisis in solving the problems involving indeterminant and inconsistent data due to inadequacy of parametrization tools. The idea of neutrosophic set as an approach for solving issues that cover unreliable, indeterminacy and persistent data was studied by Smarandache [19]. Wang et.al. [24] introduced single valued neutrosophic sets. Peng et al. [12] studied operations of neutrosophic numbers and introduced the idea of neutrosophic numbers. Neutrosophic topological space was introduced by Salama et.al. [14]

in 2012. This was studied by many mathematicians [15, 17, 18]. The idea of neutrosophic soft set was initiated by Maji [8]. Iswaraya et.al. [7] studied the concept of neutrosophic semi-open sets and neutrosophic semi-closed sets. Arokiarani et.al. [1] defined neutrosophic semi-open (resp. pre-open and α -open) functions and investigated their relations. Rao et.al. [22] introduced neutrosophic pre-open sets. P. Evanzalin Ebenanjar et.al. [5] introduced the notion of neutrosophic b -open sets are initiated and their properties are investigated. Debnath et.al. [3] studied on neutrosophic $p\delta$ -irresolute functions in neutrosophic topological spaces. Vetrivel et.al. [23] considered the forgotten topological index and the edge forgotten index in the 3-valued logic neutrosophic graph and came up with some important theorem results and applications. Subasree and BasariKodi [13] tested the proofs and examples on heptagonal neutrosophic semi-open sets in heptagonal neutrosophic topological spaces. Smarandache [20] had an overview, examples, trend analysis, research issues, challenges and future directions on revolutionary topologies. Dey et.al. [4] studied some covering properties in neutrosophic topological spaces using neutrosophic b -open sets. Continuous property is one of the important topological properties in topological spaces. Salama, A.A. and Florentin Smarandache [16] introduced neutrosophic continuous maps. In molecular graph theory or chemical graph theory, the topological index becomes useful for testing the chemical and pharmacological properties of drug molecular structures. The Forgotten Topological index concept in neutrosophic graphs to attain some important results and its properties and application were studied in [23]. In this article, the neutrosophic b -continuous maps and strongly neutrosophic b -continuous maps are defined and their properties are investigated. The properties of neutrosophic b -connectedness and neutrosophic b -compactness are developed using neutrosophic b -continuous maps.

2. Materials and Methods

Definition 2.1. [14] Let X be a non-empty fixed set. A neutrosophic set A is an object having the form $A = \{\langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X\}$ where $\mu_A(x)$, $\sigma_A(x)$ and $\gamma_A(x)$ represents the degree of membership function, the degree of indeterminacy function and the degree of non-membership function respectively of each element $x \in X$ to the set A .

Definition 2.2. [14] Let X be a non-empty set, and let the neutrosophic sets A and B be $A = \{\langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X\}$ and $B = \{\langle x, \mu_B(x), \sigma_B(x), \gamma_B(x) \rangle : x \in X\}$. Then we may consider two possible definitions for subsets ($A \subseteq B$). That is, $A \subseteq B$ may be defined as in the following two different ways

- (1) $A \subseteq B \Leftrightarrow \mu_A(x) \leq \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \leq \sigma_B(x) \text{ and } \gamma_A(x) \geq \gamma_B(x) \forall x \in X$
- (2) $A \subseteq B \Leftrightarrow \mu_A(x) \leq \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \geq \sigma_B(x) \text{ and } \gamma_A(x) \geq \gamma_B(x) \forall x \in X$

Definition 2.3. [14] Let X be a non-empty set and let the neutrosophic sets A and B be $A = \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle, B = \langle x, \mu_B(x), \sigma_B(x), \gamma_B(x) \rangle$. Then,

1. $A \cap B$ may be defined as in the following in two different ways.

- (1) $A \cap B = \langle x, \mu_A(x) \wedge \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \wedge \sigma_B(x) \text{ and } \gamma_A(x) \vee \gamma_B(x) \rangle$
- (2) $A \cap B = \langle x, \mu_A(x) \wedge \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \vee \sigma_B(x) \text{ and } \gamma_A(x) \vee \gamma_B(x) \rangle$

2. $A \cup B$ may be defined as in the following in two different ways.

- (1) $A \cup B = \langle x, \mu_A(x) \vee \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \vee \sigma_B(x) \text{ and } \gamma_A(x) \wedge \gamma_B(x) \rangle$
- (2) $A \cup B = \langle x, \mu_A(x) \vee \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \wedge \sigma_B(x) \text{ and } \gamma_A(x) \wedge \gamma_B(x) \rangle$

Here the notations \wedge and \vee means minimum and maximum respectively.

Definition 2.4. [14] A neutrosophic topology for a non-empty set X is a family τ of neutrosophic subsets in X satisfying the following axioms :

- (1) $0_N, 1_N \in \tau$,
- (2) $G_1 \cap G_2 \in \tau$ for any $G_1, G_2 \in \tau$,
- (3) $\cup G_i \in \tau$ for every $\{G_i : i \in J\} \subseteq \tau$

The pair (X, τ) is called a neutrosophic topological space.

The elements of τ are called neutrosophic open sets. The complement of a neutrosophic open set is called a neutrosophic closed set.

Definition 2.5. [14] Let (X, τ) be neutrosophic topological space and $A = \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle$ be a neutrosophic set in X . Then the neutrosophic closure and neutrosophic interior of A are defined by

- (1) $Ncl(A) = \cap \{K : K \text{ is a neutrosophic closed set in } X \text{ and } A \subseteq K\}$
- (2) $Nint(A) = \cup \{G : G \text{ is a neutrosophic open set in } X \text{ and } G \subseteq A\}$.

It can be also shown that $Ncl(A)$ is neutrosophic closed set and $Nint(A)$ is a neutrosophic open set in X . Further,

- a) A is a neutrosophic open set if and only if $A = Nint(A)$.
- b) A is a neutrosophic closed set if and only if $A = Ncl(A)$.

Definition 2.6. Let (X, τ) be a neutrosophic topological space and let U be a neutrosophic set in X . Then, U is called a

- (1) neutrosophic α -open set [15] iff $U \subseteq Nint(Ncl(Nint(U)))$
- (2) neutrosophic semi-open set [14] iff $U \subseteq Ncl(Nint(U))$
- (3) neutrosophic pre-open set [16] iff $U \subseteq Nint(Ncl(U))$

Definition 2.7. [5] A neutrosophic set U in a neutrosophic topological space X is called a neutrosophic b -open set if $U \subseteq Nint(Ncl(U)) \cup Ncl(Nint(U))$.

Further, U is called a neutrosophic b -closed set if $U \supseteq Nint(Ncl(U)) \cap Ncl(Nint(U))$

Example 2.1. Let $X = \{a, b\}$ and $A = \langle(0.3, 0.6, 0.4), (0.6, 0.3, 0.1)\rangle$, $B = \langle(0.2, 0.5, 0.7), (0.5, 0.2, 0.4)\rangle$ be neutrosophic sets in X . Then, $\tau = \{0_N, A, B, 1_N\}$ is a neutrosophic topological space on X . Now, $A_1 = \langle(0.4, 0.6, 0.4), (0.8, 0.3, 0.4)\rangle$ is a neutrosophic b -open set.

Definition 2.8. [16] Let f be a map from a neutrosophic topological space (X, τ) to a neutrosophic topological space (Y, σ) . Then f is called a neutrosophic continuous map if the preimage of each neutrosophic open set in (Y, σ) is a neutrosophic open set in (X, τ) .

Definition 2.9. [1] Let f be a map from a neutrosophic topological space (X, τ) to a neutrosophic topological space (Y, σ) . Then f is called a neutrosophic semi-continuous map if $f^{-1}(B)$ is a neutrosophic semi-open set in X for every neutrosophic open set B in Y .

Definition 2.10. [1] Let f be a map from a neutrosophic topological space (X, τ) to a neutrosophic topological space (Y, σ) . Then f is called a neutrosophic pre-continuous map if $f^{-1}(B)$ is a neutrosophic pre-open set in X for every neutrosophic open set B in Y .

Definition 2.11. [1] Let f be a map from a neutrosophic topological space (X, τ) to a neutrosophic topological space (Y, σ) . Then f is called a neutrosophic α -continuous map if $f^{-1}(B)$ is a neutrosophic α -open set in X for every neutrosophic open set B in Y .

Definition 2.12. [9] A neutrosophic topological space X is neutrosophic b -disconnected space if there exist neutrosophic b -open sets A and B in X , with $A \neq 0_N, B \neq 0_N$ such that $A \cup B = 1_N$ and $A \cap B = 0_N$. If X is not a neutrosophic b -disconnected space, then it is said to be a neutrosophic b -connected space.

Definition 2.13. [21] A neutrosophic topological space (X, τ) is said to be a neutrosophic b -compact space if each neutrosophic b -open cover of X has a finite sub-cover.

3. Results

Lemma 3.1. Every neutrosophic α -open set is a neutrosophic b -open set in a neutrosophic topological space X .

Proof. Let A be a neutrosophic α -open set in a neutrosophic topological space X . Then $A \subseteq Nint[Ncl(Nint(A))]$ which implies that, $A \subseteq Nint(Ncl(A)) \subseteq Nint(Ncl(A)) \cup Ncl(Nint(A))$. Thus A is a neutrosophic b -open set. \square

It was shown in [17] that every neutrosophic semi-open set is a neutrosophic b -open set and also every neutrosophic pre-open set is a neutrosophic b -open set.

Definition 3.1. Let f be a map from a neutrosophic topological space (X, τ) to a neutrosophic topological space (Y, σ) . Then f is said to be a neutrosophic b -continuous map if $f^{-1}(B)$ is a neutrosophic b -open set in X for every neutrosophic open set B in Y .

Example 3.1. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $Y = \{a, b, c\}$. Define neutrosophic sets A, B and C as follows: $A = \langle (0.5, 0.5, 0.5), (0.4, 0.5, 0.5), (0.4, 0.5, 0.5) \rangle$, $B = \langle (0.3, 0.4, 0.4), (0.7, 0.5, 0.5), (0.3, 0.4, 0.4) \rangle$, and $C = \langle (0.3, 0.4, 0.4), (0.3, 0.3, 0.3), (0.4, 0.5, 0.5) \rangle$.

Let $\tau = \{0_N, A, B, 1_N\}$ be a neutrosophic topological space on X and $\sigma = \{0_N, C, 1_N\}$ be a neutrosophic topological space on Y . Define $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ by $f(a) = c, f(b) = a, f(c) = b$. Then, f is a neutrosophic b -continuous map.

Theorem 3.2. A mapping $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is neutrosophic b -continuous if and only if the inverse image of every neutrosophic closed set in Y is a neutrosophic b -closed set in X .

Proof. Suppose that $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a neutrosophic b -continuous map and let B be a neutrosophic closed set in Y . Then $(Y - B)$ is neutrosophic open set in Y . Since f is neutrosophic b -continuous map, $f^{-1}(Y - B) = X - f^{-1}(B)$ is a neutrosophic b -open set in X . Hence $f^{-1}(B)$ is a neutrosophic b -closed set in X .

Conversely suppose that $f^{-1}(B)$ is a neutrosophic b -closed set in X for every neutrosophic closed set B in Y . Let U be a neutrosophic open set in Y . $Y - U$ is neutrosophic closed in Y and by hypothesis, $f^{-1}(Y - U)$ is a neutrosophic closed set in (X, τ) and therefore, $f^{-1}(U)$ is a neutrosophic b -open set in (X, τ) . Thus f is a neutrosophic b -continuous map. \square

Proposition 3.1. Every neutrosophic continuous map is a neutrosophic b -continuous map.

Proof. Let (X, τ) and (Y, σ) be two neutrosophic topological spaces. Let $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a neutrosophic continuous map and let U be a neutrosophic open set in Y . Since f is neutrosophic continuous, $f^{-1}(U)$ is neutrosophic open set in X . Since every neutrosophic open set is neutrosophic b -open set, $f^{-1}(U)$ is a neutrosophic b -open set in X . Thus f is a neutrosophic b -continuous map. \square

Converse of the above proposition need not be true in general. This can be shown in the following example:

Example 3.3. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $Y = \{a, b, c\}$. Define Neutrosophic sets A, B and C as follows: $A = \langle (0.5, 0.5, 0.5), (0.4, 0.5, 0.5), (0.4, 0.5, 0.5) \rangle$, $B = \langle (0.3, 0.4, 0.4), (0.7, 0.5, 0.5), (0.3, 0.4, 0.4) \rangle$, and $C = \langle (0.3, 0.4, 0.4), (0.3, 0.3, 0.3), (0.4, 0.5, 0.5) \rangle$.

Let $\tau = \{0_N, A, B, 1_N\}$ be a neutrosophic topological space on X and let $\sigma = \{0_N, C, 1_N\}$ is a neutrosophic topological space on Y . Define $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ by $f(a) = c, f(b) = a, f(c) = b$. Then, clearly f is a neutrosophic b -continuous map; but not a neutrosophic continuous map.

Proposition 3.2. *Let f be a map from a neutrosophic topological space (X, τ) to a neutrosophic topological space (Y, σ) . If f is neutrosophic α -continuous map, then f is neutrosophic b -continuous map.*

Proof. Let U be a neutrosophic open set in (Y, σ) . Since f is neutrosophic α -continuous map, $f^{-1}(U)$ is neutrosophic α -open set in (X, τ) . Then $f^{-1}(U)$ is neutrosophic b -open set in (X, τ) . Hence f is a neutrosophic b -continuous map. \square

Proposition 3.3. *Let f be a map from a neutrosophic topological space (X, τ) to a neutrosophic topological space (Y, σ) . If f is neutrosophic semi-continuous map, then f is neutrosophic b -continuous map.*

Proof. Let U be a neutrosophic open set in (Y, σ) . Since f is neutrosophic semi-continuous map, $f^{-1}(U)$ is neutrosophic semi-open set in (X, τ) . Then $f^{-1}(U)$ is neutrosophic b -open set in (X, τ) by lemma 3.1. Hence f is a neutrosophic b -continuous map. \square

Proposition 3.4. *Let f be a map from a neutrosophic topological space (X, τ) to a neutrosophic topological space (Y, σ) . If f is neutrosophic pre-continuous map, then f is neutrosophic b -continuous map.*

Proof. Let U be a neutrosophic open set in (Y, σ) . Since f is neutrosophic pre-continuous map, $f^{-1}(U)$ is neutrosophic pre-open set in (X, τ) . Then, $f^{-1}(U)$ is neutrosophic b -open set in (X, τ) . Hence f is a neutrosophic b -continuous map. \square

FIGURE 1. An overview of neutrosophic semi-continuous, b -continuous, pre-continuous, and α -continuous mappings.

Theorem 3.4. Let $(X, \tau), (Y, \sigma)$ and (Z, η) be three neutrosophic topological spaces and let $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ and $g : (Y, \sigma) \rightarrow (Z, \eta)$ be two mappings. If f is a neutrosophic b -continuous map and g is a neutrosophic continuous map, then $g \circ f$ is a neutrosophic b -continuous map.

Proof. Let U be a neutrosophic open set in (Z, η) . Since g is neutrosophic continuous map, $g^{-1}(U)$ is neutrosophic open set in (Y, σ) . Now as f is neutrosophic b -continuous map, we get $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(U))$ is neutrosophic b -open set in (X, τ) . So $(g \circ f)^{-1}(U)$ is neutrosophic b -open set in (X, τ) . Thus $g \circ f$ is a neutrosophic b -continuous map. \square

If f is neutrosophic α -continuous map or neutrosophic pre-continuous map or neutrosophic semi-continuous map, Then also $g \circ f$ is a neutrosophic b -continuous map by proposition 3.3,3.4,3.5 and theorem 3.4.

Definition 3.2. A map $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ is said to be strongly neutrosophic b -continuous if $f^{-1}(B)$ is a neutrosophic b -open set in X for every neutrosophic b -open set in Y .

Example 3.5. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $Y = \{a, b, c\}$. Define neutrosophic sets A, B and C as follows : $A = \langle (0.5, 0.5, 0.5), (0.4, 0.5, 0.5), (0.4, 0.5, 0.5) \rangle$, $B = \langle (0.3, 0.4, 0.4), (0.7, 0.5, 0.5), (0.3, 0.4, 0.4) \rangle$, and $C = \langle (0.3, 0.4, 0.4), (0.3, 0.3, 0.3), (0.4, 0.5, 0.5) \rangle$.

Let $\tau = \{0_N, A, B, 1_N\}$ be a neutrosophic topological space on X and $\sigma = \{0_N, C, 1_N$ be a neutrosophic topological space on Y . Define $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ by $f(a) = c, f(b) = a, f(c) = b$. Consider $D = \langle (0.3, 0.6, 0.4), (0.6, 0.3, 0.1), (0.5, 0.2, 0.4) \rangle$ be a neutrosophic b -open set in Y . Since $f^{-1}(D)$ is a neutrosophic b -open set in Y , f is strongly neutrosophic b -continuous map.

Proposition 3.5. *Every neutrosophic strongly b -continuous map is a neutrosophic b -continuous map.*

Proof. Let (X, τ) and (Y, σ) be two neutrosophic topological spaces. Let $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a neutrosophic b -continuous map and U be a neutrosophic open set in Y . Then by theorem [21], U is a neutrosophic b -open set in Y . Since f is strongly neutrosophic b -continuous, $f^{-1}(U)$ is neutrosophic b -open set in X . Thus f is a neutrosophic b -continuous map. \square

Proposition 3.6. *Let $(X, \tau), (Y, \sigma)$ and (Z, η) be three neutrosophic topological spaces. Let $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ and $g : (Y, \sigma) \rightarrow (Z, \eta)$ be strongly neutrosophic b -continuous maps. Then the composition $g \circ f$ is also a strongly neutrosophic b -continuous map.*

Proof. Let U be a neutrosophic b -open set in (Z, η) . Since g is strongly neutrosophic b -continuous map, $g^{-1}(U)$ is neutrosophic b -open set in (Y, σ) . Now as f is also strongly neutrosophic b -continuous map, we get $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(U))$ is neutrosophic b -open set in (X, τ) . So $(g \circ f)^{-1}(U)$ is neutrosophic b -open set in (X, τ) . Thus $g \circ f$ is strongly neutrosophic b -continuous map. \square

Theorem 3.6. *Let $(X, \tau), (Y, \sigma)$ and (Z, η) be three neutrosophic topological spaces and let $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a strongly neutrosophic b -continuous map and $g : (Y, \sigma) \rightarrow (Z, \eta)$ be a neutrosophic b -continuous map, then $g \circ f$ is a neutrosophic b -continuous map.*

Proof. Let U be a neutrosophic open set in Z . Since g is neutrosophic b -continuous map, $g^{-1}(U)$ is neutrosophic b -open set in Y . Now as f is strongly neutrosophic b -continuous map, we get $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(U))$ is neutrosophic b -open set in X . So $(g \circ f)^{-1}(U)$ is neutrosophic b -open set in X . Thus $g \circ f$ is neutrosophic b -continuous map. \square

Theorem 3.7. *The image of a neutrosophic b -connected space under a surjective neutrosophic b -continuous map is a neutrosophic b -connected space.*

Proof. Let $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a neutrosophic b -continuous map from a neutrosophic topological space X onto a neutrosophic topological space Y and X be a neutrosophic b -connected space. Suppose Y is neutrosophic b -disconnected. Then there exist two neutrosophic b -open sets B and C such that $B \cup C = 1_N$ and $B \cap C = 0_N$. Thus $f^{-1}(B) \cup f^{-1}(C) = f^{-1}(B \cup C) = f^{-1}(1_N) = 1_N$ and $f^{-1}(B) \cap f^{-1}(C) = f^{-1}(B \cap C) = f^{-1}(0_N) = 0_N$ which is a contradiction. Hence Y is a neutrosophic b -connected space. \square

Theorem 3.8. *The image of neutrosophic b -compact space under a surjective neutrosophic b -continuous map is neutrosophic compact space.*

Proof. Let $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ be a neutrosophic b -continuous map from a neutrosophic topological space X onto a neutrosophic topological space Y . Let $\{G_\lambda : \lambda \in \Delta\}$ be an neutrosophic open cover for Y . Then $\{f^{-1}(G_\lambda) : \lambda \in \Delta\}$ is a neutrosophic b -open cover for X . Since X is neutrosophic b -compact, this neutrosophic b open cover has a finite sub cover $\{f^{-1}(G_\lambda) : \lambda = 1, \dots, n\}$. Since f is onto, $\{G_{\lambda:\lambda=1,\dots,n}\}$ be a finite cub cover for Y . Thus Y is neutrosophic compact space. \square

Theorem 3.9. *Let (X, τ) and (Y, σ) be two neutrosophic topological spaces and let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a neutrosophic strongly b -continuous map. If the neutrosophic set A is neutrosophic b -compact in (X, τ) then $f(A)$ is neutrosophic b -compact in (Y, σ) .*

Proof. Let $B = \{G_\lambda : \lambda \in \Delta\}$ be an neutrosophic open cover of $f(A)$, where $G_\lambda \in (Y, \sigma)$ for each $\lambda \in \Delta$. Then $f(A) \subseteq \cup_{\lambda \in \Delta} G_\lambda \Rightarrow f^{-1}(f(A)) \subseteq f^{-1}(\cup_{\lambda \in \Delta} G_\lambda) \Rightarrow f^{-1}(f(A)) \subseteq \cup_{\lambda \in \Delta} f^{-1}(G_\lambda) \Rightarrow A \subseteq \cup_{\lambda \in \Delta} f^{-1}(G_\lambda)$. Since G_λ is b -open neutrosophic set in Y , so $f^{-1}(G_\lambda)$ is b -open neutrosophic set in X as f is neutrosophic strongly b -continuous. Therefore $C = \{f^{-1}G_\lambda : \lambda \in \Delta\}$ is an neutrosophic b -open cover of A . Since A is neutrosophic b -compact, so C has a finite neutrosophic b -open sub cover $\{f^{-1}G_\lambda : \lambda = 1, \dots, n\}$. Therefore $A \subseteq \cup_{i=1}^n f^{-1}(G_\lambda) \Rightarrow f(A) \subseteq f(\cup_{i=1}^n f^{-1}G(\lambda)) \Rightarrow f(A) \subseteq \cup_{i=1}^n f(f^{-1}(G_\lambda)) \Rightarrow f(A) \subseteq \cup_{i=1}^n G_\lambda$. Thus the neutrosophic b -open cover B of $f(A)$ has a finite neutrosophic b -open sub cover. Therefore $f(A)$ is neutrosophic b -compact in (Y, σ) . \square

Remark 3.1. Every neutrosophic b -compact space is a neutrosophic semi-compact space, neutrosophic pre-compact space and neutrosophic α -compact space.

4. Conclusions

Here we studied some notions of neutrosophic b -open sets and further we discussed some new properties related to neutrosophic b -open sets. we discussed some relationship of neutrosophic b -open sets with neutrosophic semi-open, neutrosophic pre-open and neutrosophic α -open sets. We defined and investigated some properties of neutrosophic b -continuous and strongly neutrosophic b -continuous maps. Finally, we developed some properties of neutrosophic b -connectedness and neutrosophic b -compactness using neutrosophic b -continuous maps.

Acknowledgments: The authors are highly thankful to the editor and referees for the valuable comments and suggestions for improving the quality of the paper.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in the research.

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Received: May 30, 2025. Accepted: Nov 11, 2025